

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH CARTOONS AND MOVIES TO
INCREASE LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH.

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Annotation: *The article below is about the role of cartoons and movies, in order*

to increase not only speaking and listening skills, but also GE (General English).

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It is true that, nowadays most language learners are suffering from not enough high level of listening and speaking skills, while other foreign language learners doing easy for speaking and listening. There are strong reasons behind my confidence, why it is impossible increasing level of English even in long term study. Now we discuss both causes and solutions to this issue. Firstly, more and more pupils tend to be learning foreign languages in their early ages, but unfortunately parents cannot help them to choose right way and sometimes teachers also. They may choose best teacher but they don't control tasks doing or another way some teachers cannot teach them in sufficient way. How? They teach them with grammar rules, every day they give them new words in order to increase their vocabulary. But one and big issue is that they don't teach them how to practice the information on their mind.

Coming from my own experience, lots of time I come across such kind of methods. What I mean is that, for instance, we can get as an example tutors one General English lesson, teacher provide students with completely grammar with its secrets, teachers are learn vocabulary by heard to students and they asked only what they teach not on language with lots of practice. At that time, pupils used to be hungry to practice, but teachers don't choose the practice way. It is one of the wrong method teaching General English. General English does not exist only with grammar rules, structures or with topic or nontopic vocabularies. GE is the whole language. It consists of all skills: listening, reading, writing and speaking. (I can give you advice best book to increase GE is **SOLUTIONS**). Secondly, the big pain is teachers cannot choose appropriate authentic materials for their students, they only choose popular one among school or learning centers) you know, there are tons of book which is unnecessary for whom just begin to learn languages. Best solution to these useless method is choosing write scheme of learning language. Pupils not ought to disappoint with such kind of boring ways.

Although many people consider adventure cartoons childish and inappropriate for adults, we don't share the same opinion. For us, it is an extremely great way to practice different language skills while simply having fun. Moreover, some animated films are created specifically for adult audiences, sometimes providing more exciting plots and character developments than actual movies. Today, we'll help you discover the benefits of watching cartoons for English learning and provide the best options to get started. Although many people consider adventure cartoons childish and inappropriate for adults, we don't share the same opinion. For us, it is an extremely great way to practice different language skills while simply having fun. Moreover, some animated films are created specifically for adult audiences, sometimes providing more exciting plots and character developments than actual movies. Today, we'll help you discover the benefits of watching cartoons for English learning and provide the best options to get started.

Tips for Choosing Cartoons for Learning English

Watching English cartoons can enhance your listening skills, expand your vocabulary, and improve general language comprehension. However, you must find the most suitable option to achieve the best results. With so many English cartoons available, this task may be challenging. But don't worry – we know how to help. Here are some useful tips to find the cartoon that will be perfect for you.

Consider your current proficiency level. It is essential, as it makes your learning process easy and seamless. For beginners, opt for shows with simple language and clear pronunciation. As you progress, challenge yourself with more complex dialogues and vocabulary.

Find cartoons in English that might be interesting to you. Language, themes, and storylines differ between shows created for kids, teens, and adults. Therefore, it is vital to choose the option that you really want to watch and that will keep you engaged while studying.

Determine your goals. Before watching, consider the results you want from a particular cartoon. If your final goal is to improve your listening skills, choose a show full of vivid dialogues and conversations. In case you want to expand your vocabulary, pick cartoons that picture daily life and casual interactions between characters. These tips are enough to find numerous cartoons to learn English and select the best one for yourself. We've compiled the best shows for various fluency levels to simplify the process even more. So, without further ado, let's check them out!

From Beginner to Advanced: Best Cartoons for Learning English

No matter movie, documentary, or cartoon, finding the one that suits your proficiency level is vital. Otherwise, you will get lost in complex vocabulary,

intricate lines, and hard-to-understand dialogues. If you don't know your level, you can pass a quick test, but if you do, look at the list of the best English cartoons for learning English

Stating all of my experience and my instructors lessons I realize that, there are big role of English cartoons and movies not only learning languages but also increasing the levels of skills. If you are rich of doing practice and watching English movies cartoons or listening that languages music is really helpful method. If I speak from my side, I always watch cartoons and movies with subtitles according to my level, and this method greatly help me to rise me more high than others. I hate from practicing, it is just wasting time, true it is necessary but you should practice max 3 or 4 times a week. IELTS is not just skill testing test it tests your whole English. Instructors' brilliant advice is separate your time watching English authentic recourses than learning by heart complex grammar structures or topic vocabulary. This method is extremely useful, because you can find everything with them. It includes all of them grammar vocabulary body and whole languages even.

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